

The Effect of Product Quality, Timeline and Customer Focus on Risk Management at PT PLN Enjiniring

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Abstract:- Many factors that cause failure in the implementation of construction can occur. For this reason, careful planning is needed in the design, so the quality of the product must be considered. Risk management in the implementation of construction planning is important to note. Based on this, the researchers conducted risk management research by looking at product quality, timeliness and customer service at the consulting company PT PLN Enjiniring so that they could determine the effect. In this study, data was collected through a questionnaire method to 100 respondents at Internal PLN Engineering using purposive sampling method to determine respondents' responses to each variable. Then an analysis of the data obtained in the form of quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis was carried out. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis which serves to prove the research hypothesis. The data that has met the validity test, reliability test, and classical assumption test were processed using the SPSS program. The results of multiple linear regression analysis found that product quality, timeliness and customer service had a positive relationship with risk management. The influence of timeliness and customer service on risk management has a significant effect, while product quality on risk management shows an insignificant effect.

Keywords:- Multiple Linear Regression, Product Quality, Risk Management, Service Delivery, Timeliness,

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background to the Problem

Many factors that cause failures in the implementation of construction can occur. For this reason, it is necessary to have careful planning on the design, so the quality of the product must be considered. Failed construction or makrak becomes a risk of PLN. Risk management in the implementation of construction planning is important to pay attention to. According to McIntyre et al (2013) the success of construction projects depends largely on the ability of the project manager to manage the risks that occur. According to Hopkinson (2011) risk management is an activity carried out to respond to known risks. Meanwhile, the Project Management Institute (2012) formulated risk management including steps related to efforts

to implement risk management planning, identification, response, and monitoring and supervision of a project. According to Kotler and Keller (2016: 156) product quality is one of the keys to competition among business actors offered to consumers. Meanwhile, *customer focus* is an effort to fulfill something or make something adequate Tjiptono (2016: 204). A product is said to be of high quality if it meets the needs and desires of buyers. Quality is determined by customers and their experience of products and services.

By comparing the target data and the realization data, this deviation is obtained which is the initial data as a reference in conducting research. There needs to be further analysis related to risk management and engineering services, especially construction failures that may occur in the PT PLN Enjiniring Project, so that by conducting this research, it is hoped that it can have an impact on product quality, punctuality and *customer focus* can achieve KPI targets and construction failures can be anticipated to a minimum.

According to Sutawidjaya (2019) that integrated risk management is a process used by every organization to calculate, control, utilize, finance, and monitor risks from all sources in order to increase short-term and long-term value for company stakeholders.

B. Research Objectives

Based on the explanation above, this study aims to find out, analyze the strength and direction of influence:

1. Product quality to risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring.
2. Timeliness of risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring.
3. *Customer* focuses on risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring.

II. THEORETICAL STUDIES

A. Risk Management

According to Nugroho (2019) interpreting risk as a form of uncertainty about a situation that will occur later (*future*) with decisions taken based on considerations at this time. Risk management is a field of science that discusses how an organization sets measures in mapping various existing problems with various management approaches in a comprehensive and systematic manner.

The company's process of producing quality work results with good company management, management here is to discuss the process in planning steps to produce maximum work results. In general, management is defined as a process, identifying, measuring, and ascertaining risks and developing strategies to manage those risks (Lokobal, 2014).

As for according to Schlagel and Trent (2015), risks can be categorized as follows:

- Risiko Strategis (Strategic Risk)
- Hazard Risk
- Financial Risk
- Operational Risk

B. Product Quality

Product quality according to Kotler and Armstrong (2015: 236), is the characteristic of a product or service that corresponds to its ability to meet the stated or implied needs of the customer. Product quality is one of the main positioning tools of a marketer. According to Kotler in A Claudia (2019), the higher the level of quality, the higher the level of satisfaction felt by consumers, with the high satisfaction felt by consumers, consumers will recommend products to others. Then it can be concluded that product quality is the character or trait possessed by a product that can meet the needs or desires of a person.

Sangadji et al (2013: 329) explained that there are six elements of product quality, namely: performance, reliability, features, durability, conformity with specifications, design. From the opinion of Sangadji et al, it can be concluded that the dimension of product quality is an element that is used as a measure in determining a quality product and can be used continuously. The quality dimension is a requirement that a product's value allows it to satisfy consumers as expected, while the product quality dimension includes performance, aesthetics, privileges, reliability, and design.

C. Timeliness

According to Handoko, (2010) punctuality is the period of time consumers order products until the product arrives in the hands of consumers. The estimated arrival is usually a benchmark for consumers to find out whether the delivery service is good or not (Hafizha, et al, 2019). According to Aminah, (2017: 50) punctuality is "The ability of suppliers to deliver on time in minimal batches. Then begin to evaluate based on the distance between the supplier and the company, their production capacity and the historical proficiency of workers to deliver on time". Then according to Sakti and Mahfudz (2018: 3) punctuality is very important, considering that the accuracy of the sender of ordered products will be an important factor in increasing customer focus.

According to Widhiawati in (Wisudanto, 2013) project delays will cause losses on the part of contractors, consultants, and owners. As for the reckoning of delays in the completion of work as follows:

1. Lack of understanding of the content of the contract
2. Changes in the scope of work
3. Late work of subcontractors.

D. Customer Focus

Customer focus is the orientation of the series of services provided to customers. Kotler (2008) mentioned that um satisfaction (satisfaction) is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment of a person that arises from comparing the perceived performance of the product (results) to their expectations. If the performance does not meet expectations, then the customer will be dissatisfied, on the contrary, if the performance is in accordance with expectations, the customer will be satisfied. Furthermore, if the performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied or happy. Those customer expectations come from past buying experiences, the advice of friends and associates, and the information and promises of marketers and competitors. However, if companies set expectations that are too low, they will not be able to attract enough buyers.

Customer-centric marketing is an attempt to understand and satisfy the needs, wants and resources of potential customers (Sheth et al, 2000). By understanding this, it is hoped that the company can create value and increase satisfaction for customers. To build an effective *customer focus*, here are some strategies that can be done: strengthen collaboration, make customers feel heard, use criticism and suggestions from customers, use data and empathy, and use multiple channels

E. Past Research

Previous research according to Yuliana (2017) that risk mitigation is carried out in order to reduce the risks that affect the occurrence of contract addendums due to non-conformity in cost, quality and time, as well as avoid sanctions for late fees and termination of contracts by the project owner to the implementing contractor. The results of research by Sari et al (2020) can be concluded that any improvement in product quality and service quality can encourage an increase in customer satisfaction both individually and simultaneously. Taken together, changes in product quality outweigh the changes in service to customer satisfaction. The results of the study by Fransiska Moi et al (2021) namely from the results of the analysis obtained 2 High risks that caused a significant impact, namely the rejection of residents to land acquisition and damage to equipment (heavy equipment) resulting in delays. Meanwhile, medium risk that is most likely to occur can have a significant impact. Ownership of the risk at major risk is borne by the contractor where this risk occurs at the stage before the road construction project is underway and at the time the construction project is underway.

F. Frame of Mind

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a formulation of a research problem, where the formulation of a research problem has been expressed in the form of a question sentence. It says interim, because the answers given are based on relevant theories, it has not based on empirical facts obtained through data collection. So that the hypothesis can also be expressed as a theoretical answer to a formulation of a research problem (Sugiyono, 2017).

This is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig 1:- Research Steps

Source: Wijayanto (2017) processed by the author (2022) in the data analysis process.

G. Hypothesis

Some hypotheses can be established are as follows:

- Hypothesis 1: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between product quality variables (X1) on Risk Management (Y)
- Hypothesis 2: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the timeliness variables (X2) on Risk Management (Y)
- Hypothesis 3: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the customer focus variable (X3) on Risk Management (Y).
- Hypothesis 4: It is suspected that there is a significant influence between product quality (X1), punctuality (X2), customer focus (X3) on risk management (Y).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study belongs to the survey category (descriptive and correlational), and not the experimental category. This study is intended to analyze risk management factors that affect product quality, punctuality and customer focus (Case Study of PT. PLN Enjiniring). This research method or approach is quantitative, which is intended to measure something with precision. Meanwhile, the research method used in this study was a survey, using a questionnaire instrument in collecting data. Then the data from the questionnaire will be analyzed using the help of SPSS tools.

The data analysis used in this study is a method of multiple linear regression analysis. Here's the multiple linear regression equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

A. Data Analysis Methods

This study used adouble beng linear regression analysis method. Where according to Suhardi and Puwanto (2004) Your berg linear regression analysis is a linear regression to analyze the magnitude of the relationship and the influence of

independent variables whose number of variables is more than two. The research uses a quantitative approach using research instruments in the form of questionnaires. The stages carried out in the distribution of this research questionnaire are 2 stages, namely.

➤ First Stage Questionnaire (Preliminary Survey)

At this preliminary survey stage, it is to determine the free variables that will be used as variables for this study by ranking with the relative importance index (RII) method. The following are free variables of product quality factors, time determination and customer focus which will be arranged based on the acquisition of their weight value which will be discussed in the results and discussion in this study with a likert scale of 1-5 where, 1 = very no effect, 2 = no effect, 3 = less influential, 4= influential, 5= very influential. From the data obtained from the respondents, validity and reliability tests were carried out with SPSS tools.

➤ Second Stage Questionnaire (Advanced Survey)

After obtaining the ranking of variables of product quality factors, time determination and customer focus on the first stage of the questionnaire, followed by the second stage of questionnaire in this study consisting of 2 research variables, namely as follows:

- Independent or free variables (X) namely Factors of product quality, punctuality and customer focus (Results of the first stage of questionnaire ranking based on the resulting weight value).
- Dependent or bound variables (Y) i.e., risk management.

In this second stage of the questionnaire, the respondents gave a value to each variable of product quality factors, time provisions, customer focus on product quality, with a likert scale of 1-5 From the data obtained from the respondents, validity and reliability tests were carried out with SPSS software tools.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Based on the results of the study, the characteristics of PT PLN Enjiniring employees can be seen in Table 1.

No.	Variable	Answer	Sum	Percentage
1	Gender	Man	79	79.0
		Woman	21	21.0
		Total	33	100.0
2	Age	>20 – 30 Year	42	42.0
		>31 - 40 Year	28	28.0
		> 41- 50 Year	20	20.0
		> 50 year	10	10.0
		Total	100	100.0
3	Position	Staff	82	82.0
		Manager	12	12.0
		Vice President	2	2.0
		Director	1	1.0
		Total	100	100.0

Table 1:- Characteristics of Respondents
Source: Processed data (2022)

Based on Table 1. it is known that the majority of respondents are male, while in terms of age the majority of respondents are between 20-30 years old. These characteristics show that the majority of employees at PT PLN Enjiniring are male and aged between 20-30 years. Based on the position, the majority of respondents are staff. This is because when the research was carried out, several respondents of employees who had just entered PT PLN Enjiniring between 1 to 5 years.

Instrument testing of the questionnaire is carried out before the analysis of the hypothesis is submitted and used as a tool for collecting primary data. Instrument tests include validity tests and instrument reliability tests. From the results of statistical tests on the validity of product quality variables, it shows that of the 18 points of the statement and 15 points of the statement are valid. Statistical reliability tests showed that the value of Cronbach alpha was 0.978. Thus, all items are declared reliable because the value of Cronbach alpha is above the minimum limit of 0.70, so it can be concluded that the measurement scale of product quality variables has good reliability.

From the statistical test results of the validity of the punctuality variable, it shows that all 8 points of the statement are valid. Reliability statistical tests showed that the value of Cronbach alpha was 0.977. Thus, all grains are declared reliable because the Cronbach alpha value is above the minimum limit of 0.70, so it can be concluded that the timeliness measurement scale has good reliability.

From the statistical test results of the validity of the customer focus variable, it shows that all 11 points of the statement are valid. Reliability statistical tests showed that the value of Cronbach alpha was 0.977. Thus, all items are declared reliable because the Cronbach alpha value is above the minimum limit of 0.70, so it can be concluded that the customer focus measurement scale has good reliability.

B. Classical Assumption Test Results

In multiple linear regression analysis, it is required that the research data meet some classical assumptions. **The Normality Test** is performed to find out whether the data has a normal distribution or not. Based on the figures The normality test used in this study is the nonparametric statistical test Kolmogorov Smirnov test, where the significance value must show a number above 0.05 of 0.087 which means that the data has been distributed normally. **The Multicollinearity test** was performed to see whether there were strong relationships between the free variables. The results of the multicollinearity test showed that the VIF value of the product quality variable was 5,717, the vif value of punctuality was 4,796 and the VIF value of the customer focus variable was 5,705. Thus, all variables have a VIF value of < 10, so it can be concluded that the regression model does not have a correlation between independent variables.

C. Multiple Linear Regression

The effect of product quality, punctuality and customer focus on risk management can be seen in Table 2.

Model	B	t	F	Sig
Constant	0.293	0,168		0,867
Product Quality	0.011	0.187		0,852
Timeliness	0.357	3.722		0,000
Customer Focus	0.249	3.052		0.003
R Square	0,710			
F hit			78.168	0,000

Table 2:- Effect of product quality (X1), punctuality (X2), customer focus (X3) on risk management (Y)

Source: Primary Data Processed (2022)

The value of R Square is 0.710. The magnitude of the Coefficient of Determination is 71.00%. These results showed that the free variables used in this study were able to influence the variation in changes in bound variables by 71.00%, while the remaining 29.00% was influenced by other variables that were not included in this study.

The t-test is performed to compare the calculated t-value with the table's t-value. If t count > t the table is said to have a significant effect and if t counts < t the table, it says the effect is insignificant.

In Table 2 sig column, for the product quality variable, it can be seen that the sig value is 0.852, smaller than 0.05, then it can be concluded that the product quality has no significant effect. Significance testing can also be performed by comparing the calculated t-value with the table t. The table t values for N= 100 and alpha 0.05 are 1.995. The value of t counting the leadership variable is 1,187, this means that t counts < t of the table, then Ha is rejected, and Ho is accepted. Thus, product quality has a positive and insignificant influence on risk management.

In Table 2 sig column, for the achievement punctuality variable, it can be seen that the sig value is 0.000, less than 0.05, then it can be concluded that punctuality has a significant effect. Significance testing can also be performed by comparing the calculated t-value with the table t. The table t values for N= 100 and alpha 0.05 are 1.995. The value of t counting the timeliness variable is 3,052, this means that t counts > t of the table, then Ha is accepted, and Ho is rejected. Thus, punctuality has a positive and significant influence on risk management.

In Table 2 sig column, for the outstanding customer focus variable, it can be seen that the sig value is 0.000, smaller than 0.05, so it can be concluded that customer focus has a significant effect. Significance testing can also be performed by comparing the calculated t-value with the table t. The table t values for N= 100 and alpha 0.05 are 1.995. The value of t counting the customer focus variable is 3,052, this means that t count > t table, then Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected. Thus, customer focus has a positive and significant influence on risk management.

Based on Sutrisni (2020) in his research that companies need to improve product quality because good product quality will cause customer satisfaction in a product so that it encourages repurchases on the same brand. It is this repurchase that will give rise to customer loyalty. The results of the research by Alrizal et al (2020) can be concluded that the factors that greatly influence the delay of work in the first rank are the categories of aspects of planning, scheduling and coordination with changing work plan factors. The results of research by Agridama et al (2018) namely the factors that most predominantly cause delays in construction project construction work are design changes by the owner, delays in material delivery, limited material availability, late payment to workers, the owner's payment system to contractors who are not in accordance with the contract due to certain reasons.

According to research by Simanjuntak et al (2020) that it is very important in project management to carry out a risk management process based on existing knowledge, one of which is the basis of the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) and pay attention to risk mitigation recommendations from previous studies that are relevant to avoid project delays.

The equation of multiple regression lines obtained is:

$$Y = 0.293 + 0.011X1 + 0.357X2 + 0.249X3$$

From the equation above the coefficient of linear regression bergThe company above can be interpreted as follows:

1. The constant coefficient of the company is positive and insignificant states that assuming the absence of product quality variables (X1), punctuality (X2) and customer focus (X3), then risk management (Y) has increased by 0.293 units. then risk management (Y) will experience an increase of 0.293 units and have an insignificant effect on risk management.
2. The regression coefficient is positive and insignificant to product quality (X1), states that the quality of the product (X1) assuming the absence of other independent variables, then in the event of an increase, then the risk management increases by 0.011 units.
3. The regression coefficient is positive and significant to punctuality (X2), assuming there are no other independent variables, so that if the timeliness (X2), then risk management increases by 0.357 units.
4. Regression coefficient is positive and significant to customer focus (X3), assuming there are no other independent variables, so that if the customer focus (X3), then risk management increases by 0.249 units.

D. Correlation Matrix Between Dimensions

The correlation matrix between dimensions shows the relationship between the dimensions of independent variables and the dimensions of dependent variables. The results of each of these relationships will be analyzed as per Table 3.

Variable	X1 (Kualitas Produk)					X2 (Ketepatan Waktu)			
	X1.1 (Kinerja)	X1.2 (Keandalan)	X1.3 (Keistimewaan tambahan)	X1.4 (Daya Tahan)	X1.5 (Kesesuaian dengan spesifikasi)	X1.6 (Desain)	X2.1 (tidak paham kontrak)	X2.2 (Perubahan lingkup kerja)	X2.3 (Subkon terlambat)
Manajemen Risiko Y1 (Risiko Operasional)	0,585	0,525	0,477	0,599	0,516	0,398	0,621	0,605	0,674
Manajemen Risiko Y2 (risiko Finansial)	0,491	0,605	0,563	0,591	0,641	0,473	0,660	0,643	0,550

Variable	X3 (Customer Focus)				
	X3.1 (Mempererat kolaborasi)	X3.2 (Pelanggan Merasa Didengar)	X3.3 (Kritik dan Saran dari Pelanggan)	X3.4 (Data dan Empati)	X3.5 (Banyak Channel)
Manajemen Risiko Y1 (Risiko Operasional)	0,499	0,501	0,616	0,657	0,518
Manajemen Risiko Y2 (risiko Finansial)	0,592	0,589	0,676	0,627	0,629

■ Nilai tolerasi terbesar
■ Nilai tolerasi terkecil

Table 3:- Correlation Matrix Between Dimensions
Source: Author's Processed Data (2022)

An analysis of the dimensions between independent variables and dependent variables was carried out as follows:

1. The correlation of the design dimensions on the product quality variable (X1) with the dimensions on the Risk Management variable (Y) shows: that the product quality variable, namely in the design dimension, has a correlation coefficient value that has a positive relationship with the operational risk dimension of 0.398 with a significant level of 0.05. This explains that the design dimension is able to influence risk management in the operational risk dimension with a fairly low degree of influence. For the design dimensions, it has a correlation coefficient value of 0.473 with a significant level of 0.05. So that the design dimension is able to influence risk management variables through the financial risk dimension with a fairly strong / moderate degree of influence. That the correlation between the performance and design dimensions in the product quality variable and the dimension in the risk management variable has a positive value, which means that the greater the quality product to the work in achieving the goals of the organization, the higher the management controls the risks that will be proven in the results of the work.
2. The correlation of the late subcon dimension on the punctuality variable (X2) with the dimension dimension on the risk management variable (Y) shows: that the punctuality variable, namely in the late subcon dimension, has a correlation coefficient value that has a positive relationship with the financial risk dimension of 0.550 with a significant level of 0.01. This explains that the subconception dimension is able to influence risk management in the financial risk dimension with a fairly strong / moderate degree of influence. That the correlation between the dimension of the late subcon in the variable of punctuality and the dimension in the variable of risk management has a positive value, which means that the greater the product of the late subcon to the product produced in the achievement of the objectives of the organization, the higher the management controls the risk that will be proved in the results of the work.

3. The correlation of the dimension of strengthening collaboration on the *customer focus* variable (X3) with the dimension dimension on the risk management variable (Y) shows: that the *customer focus* variable, namely in the dimension of strengthening collaboration, has a correlation coefficient value that has a positive relationship with the operational risk dimension of 0.499 with a significant level of 0.01. This explains that the dimension of strengthening collaboration is able to influence risk management in the dimension of operational risk with a fairly strong / moderate degree of influence. That the correlation between the dimensions of strengthening collaboration in the *customer focus* variable and the dimension in the risk management variable has a positive value, which means that the greater the collaboration with work in achieving organizational goals, the higher the management controls the risks that will be proven in the results of work.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion.

1. Positive and insignificant effect between product quality and risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring
2. Positive and significant effect between punctuality and risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring.
3. Positive and significant effect between Customer Focus on risk management at PT PLN Enjiniring.
4. Together, product quality factors, punctuality & Customer Focus affect risk management.

B. Suggestion

Based on the results of the research obtained, the author proposed several suggestions that are expected to be input for parties interested in this research. These suggestions include:

1. The author suggests to PT PLN Enjiniring to make the following improvements:
 - a. In the quality of the product that needs to be improved, namely the existence (X1.2) with moderate to strong choleration so that it greatly affects financial risks while for design (X1.6) with weak choleration so that it slightly affects financial risks.
 - b. In timeliness that needs to be improved, namely the late subcontractor (X2.3) conveys its products with moderate to strong choleration values so as to affect financial risks and operational risks while the other dimensions are also the choleration value is strong.
 - c. In Customer Focus, what needs to be improved is criticism and suggestions (X3.3) provided by the employer, which is followed up to improve products with moderate to strong choleration values so as to affect financial risks and operational risks while the dimension of strengthening collaboration (X3.1) with a moderate choleration value so that it can affect financial risks.
2. For employees, the author suggests that in carrying out work, they must pay attention to product quality, punctuality, Customer Focus so that there are no repeated complaints so as to reduce the employer's trust in the resulting product.

3. For subsequent studies, the authors suggested that it should be necessary to increase the number of samples and expand the area of research so that the level of generalization is higher.

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